

Spectrophotometric determination of cobalt in biological samples using 2-acetylpyridine semicarbazone

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Abstract : Analytical application of 2-acetylpyridine thiosemicarbazone (APT) and 2-acetylpyridine semicarbazone is described for the direct non-extractive spectrophotometric determination of cobalt. The reagents react with cobalt in acidic medium (pH 6.0, sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer) to form orange yellow colored 1 : 2 (M : L) complexes. The colour reactions are instantaneous and absorbance values remain constant for over 24 h. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of APT and APS methods are found to be 1.25×10^4 and 1.45×10^4 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.0047 and 0.004 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ of Co^{II} respectively. The systems obey Beer's law in the range of 0.236–2.357 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Co^{II}. Since APS method is more sensitive it was applied for the determination of cobalt in biological samples.

Keywords : Spectrophotometry, cobalt, 2-acetylpyridine semicarbazone, biological samples.

Introduction

Semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones¹⁻³ are important reagents widely used for the spectrophotometric determination of metal ions. Cobalt is an important essential element. It is present in vitamin B₁₂ which is involved in the production of red blood cells and the prevention of pernicious anemia⁴. Insufficient natural levels of cobalt in feed causes cobalt deficiency diseases characterized by anemia, loss of weight, or retarded growth⁵. In the light of biological role and essentiality of cobalt in living organisms it is considered worthwhile to develop new spectrophotometric method for the determination of cobalt in biological samples.

Several authors have reported on the extractive spectrophotometric determination of cobalt(II) using complexes formed by variety of reagents⁶⁻⁸. In most of the methods cited above, cobalt forms soluble/insoluble complexes with reagents in the aqueous phase, which are subsequently extracted with various solvents for spectrophotometric determination. Most of these reagents are expensive and non-recoverable.

This paper describes synthesis, characterization and analytical properties of new reagents viz. 2-acetylpyridine thiosemicarbazone (APT) and 2-acetylpyridine semicarbazone

(APS). The spectrophotometric determination of cobalt using APT and APS is included in this paper. Since the latter reagent is more sensitive, it was used for the determination of cobalt in various biological samples.

X = O, APS

X = S, APT

Results and discussion

The reagents APT and APS may be easily prepared. The reagent solutions (0.01 M) are found to be stable for 12 h. The bathochromic shift of absorption band from 290 to 300 nm indicates that in solution on increasing the pH, the acid is neutralized and the >C=S group is

enolized and dissociated⁹. The colour reactions of some important metal ions with APT and APS are summarized in Table 1. In basic medium (above pH 8.56) the ligand presumably exists in enolic form and coordinates the divalent metal ion as mono anion to give neutral complexes.

described in the standard procedure. An error of $\pm 2\%$ in the absorbance reading was considered tolerable. The tolerance limit (TL) values in ppm for various anions and cations in APT and APS methods respectively are as follows : citrate (1152, 1152); tartrate (888, 888); ascorbate

Table 1. Physico-chemical and analytical properties of Co^{II} complexes with APT and APS

Sl. no.	Characteristics	Co-APT	Co-APS
1.	λ_{\max} (nm)	355	360
2.	pH range (optimum)	5.0-8.0	5.0-8.0
3.	Mole of reagent required per mole of metal ion for full colour development	10-fold	10-fold
4.	Time stability of the complex (in hours)	24	24
5.	Beer's law validity range ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.236-2.357	0.236-1.885
6.	Molar absorptivity ($\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	1.25×10^4	1.45×10^4
7.	Specific absorptivity ($\text{ml g}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	0.212	0.24
8.	Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g of Co}^{\text{II}} \text{cm}^{-2}$)	0.0047	0.0041
9.	Composition of the complex as obtained in Job's and molar ratio methods (M : L)	1 : 2	1 : 2
10.	Stability constant of the complex	3.40×10^{13}	9.24×10^{13}
11.	Standard deviation	0.0079	0.0039
12.	Relative standard deviation (RSD)	0.56%	0.27%

Cobalt(II) reacts with APT and APS in acidic pHs to give water soluble complexes. The colour reactions are instantaneous at room temperature. The change in the order of addition of metal ion, reagent (APT or APS), buffer has no effect on the absorbance of complexes. Analytical characteristics of the complexes are summarized in Table 1. The stoichiometry of the complexes (M : L = 1 : 2) was determined by Job's continuous variation and molar ratio methods. Sodium acetate (0.2 M)-acetic acid (0.2 M) buffer solution (pH 6.0 and $T = 300 \text{ K}$) and equimolar ($4.8 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$) solutions of Co^{II} and APT or APS were used in these methods. The data obtained in Job's method were used in the calculation of stability constants of the complexes.

The effect of various cations and anions which are generally associated with the metal ion in the determination of cobalt(II) was studied by measuring the absorbance of the cobalt complexes containing 1.2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of cobalt(II) in solution. The colour reaction is developed as

(752, 752); iodate (761, 761); iodide (612, 761), thiocyanate (507, 507); phosphate (465, 465); urea (384, 384); bromide (317, 317); sulphate (252, 384); thiosulphate (246, 246), nitrate (212, 244); oxalate (281, 281); fluoride (75, 75); Ba²⁺ (675, 800); Mn²⁺ (275, 325); Mg²⁺ (125, 150); Sr²⁺ (100, 125); W⁶⁺ (110, 110); Sn²⁺ (47, 47); Pb²⁺ (41, 47); Cd²⁺ (23, 26); Mo⁶⁺ (19, 23); Ti³⁺ (14, 14); Fe²⁺ (12, 10); Cr⁶⁺ (10, 12); Zn and Pd²⁺ (10, 10), Pt⁴⁺ (8, 8); Fe³⁺ (5, 4); Au (4, 4); Ag⁺ (2, 5); Ni²⁺ (1, 1.2); Cu²⁺ (1, 1). Higher amounts of Fe³⁺ (13, 17) do not interfere in the presence of 70 ppm of fluoride. Larger amounts of Hg²⁺ (40, 48) do not interfere in the presence of 600 ppm of iodide.

The present method (APS) was applied for the determination of cobalt when present alone and present in biological samples (Table 2).

The present ligands containing heterocyclic ring are found to be potential and cost effective for the determination of cobalt(II) without the need for extraction using the

toxic solvents. Further, the reagents are easy to synthesize using commercially available precursors. Moreover, the present method is simple, rapid and very sensitive for non-extractive spectrophotometric determination of cobalt(II) in aqueous medium.

Table 2. Determination of cobalt in liver samples

Sample	Cobalt ($\mu\text{g/g}$) ^a		Recovery \pm S.D. %
	Added	Found	
Sheep liver	0	1.13	
	100	101.02	99.9 \pm 0.35
	500	502.10	100.1 \pm 0.2
Fish liver	0	1.23	
	100	101.23	100.0 \pm 0.1
	500	504.10	100.5 \pm 0.19

^aAverage of five determinations.

Experimental

Preparation of APS and APT :

The reaction mixture containing 2-acetylpyridine (5 ml, 0.044 mol), semicarbazide hydrochloride (4 g, 0.044 mol) and 50 ml of 50% aqueous methanol was taken in 250-ml round bottom flask and refluxed for 3 h. On cooling the reaction mixture, light brown coloured product was formed. It was collected by filtration and washed with hot water and 50 percent cold methanol. This compound was recrystallised from ethanol and dried *in vacuo*, yield 2.6 g; m.p. 183 °C.

The reagent (APT) was prepared by simple condensation of 1 mol of 2-acetylpyridine and 1 mol of thiosemicarbazide. In a 250-ml Erlenmeyer flask, a hot methanolic solution of 2-acetylpyridine (5 ml, 0.044 mol in 5 ml of methanol) and thiosemicarbazide (4 g, 0.044 mol, dissolved in 10 ml of hot water) were taken. Suitable quantity (~2 ml) of glacial acetic acid was added to the reaction mixture and refluxed for 3 h. On cooling the reaction mixture, light brown coloured product was separated out. It was collected by filtration and washed several times with hot water and 50 percent cold methanol. This compound was recrystallised from ethanol and dried *in vacuo*, yield 4.2 g; m.p. 175 °C.

Characterisation of APT and APS :

The reagents have been characterized by IR and ¹H NMR spectral data. Infrared spectrum of APT and APS shows bands at [3459(m), 3403(m); 3369(m,br), 3375(m,br)]; 3184(m), 3200(m); 1608(m), 1606(m); 1501(s),

1578(br); 1466(s), 1458(br); 1367(w), 1426(br); 1150(m), 1248(m); 840(δ), 842(δ); 664(δ) and 733(δ) cm^{-1} respectively corresponding to νNH asymmetric, νNH symmetric, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})$ aromatic stretch, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ stretching, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{C})$ aromatic ring, $\delta(\text{C}-\text{H})$ of pyridine ring, $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ stretch (primary amide), $\nu(\text{C}=\text{X})$ (where X=S in APT and X=O in APS), $\delta(\text{C}-\text{H})$ -oop bend (aromatic) and $\delta(\text{C}-\text{C})$ -oop bend aromatic ring vibrations. ¹H NMR spectra of APT and APS ($\text{CDCl}_3 + \text{DMSO}-d_6$) showed signals at 2.25, 2.31 (3H, s); 7.15–7.49, 7.59–7.10 (4H, m); 8.15, 8.32 (2H, s); 10.08 and 10.15 (1H, s) due to CH_3 , $\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N}$ (pyridine), $-\text{NH}_2$ and $=\text{N}-\text{NH}$ (hydrazine) proton groups of thiosemicarbazone and semicarbazone moiety.

pK_a values of reagents :

The pK_a values were determined by recording the UV-Visible spectra of $2 \times 10^{-5} M$ solutions of the reagent at various pH values and by taking the arithmetic mean of the values obtained from the measurements at different wavelengths determined spectrophotometrically using Phillips and Merrit method. The values of deprotonation of APT and APS were 5.46 and 6.61 (pK_1); 8.56 and 8.30 (pK_2).

The reagent (APT or APS) solution (0.01 M) was prepared by dissolving 50 mg of the compound in dimethylformamide (DMF) in 25-ml standard flask. The reagent solution is stable for at least 12 h.

Hydrochloric acid (1 M)-sodium acetate (1 M) (pH 0.5–3.5); 0.2 M NaOAc-0.2 M AcOH (pH 4–6) and 2 M NH_4Cl -2 M NH_4OH (pH 7–10) solutions were used.

A stock solution (1 mg L^{-1}) was prepared by dissolving 493 mg of cobalt nitrate hexahydrate $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (E. Merck preanalysis) in 100-ml de-ionized water. Hydrolysis of cobalt was prevented by adding 2 ml of 2 M HNO_3 . Dilute standard solutions were prepared from this stock solution as and when required.

Recommended procedure :

An aliquot of the solutions containing 0.24–2.36 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (or ppm) of cobalt(II), 10 ml of NaOAc-AcOH buffer solution (pH 6.0) and 1.0 ml of 0.01 M APT or APS were mixed in a 25-ml volumetric flask and resulting solution was diluted to the mark with distilled water. The absorbance of this solution was measured at 355 and 360 nm against respective reagent blank. The measured absorbance is used to compute the amount of cobalt present in the samples using predetermined calibration plot.

Note

Schimadzu 160A UV-Visible spectrophotometer equipped with 1.0 cm quartz cell and an ELICO model LI-610 pH meter were used in the present study.

Dried fish and sheep liver samples (2–5 g) were taken in a 250-ml beaker. A 6 ml of concentrated nitric acid was added and gently heated for half-an-hour. After the disappearance of the froth, 6 ml of 1 : 1 nitric acid and perchloric acid were added^{8,9}. The contents were digested for one hour and repeatedly treated with 6 ml portions of nitric acid and perchloric acid mixture until the solution becomes colourless. The acidic solution was evaporated to dryness and the resulting white residue was dissolved in minimum volume of 1 M nitric acid and made upto the volume in a 50-ml volumetric flask. Aliquots of this solution were taken for analysis following the recommended procedure.

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